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Research Article

ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING IN SPINAL TUBERCULOSIS

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Abstract:

Objective: The main idea of this research work is to assess the role of magnetic resonance imaging to examine the degree of disease of spinal TB (Tuberculosis).

Methodology: This research work was an elaborate descriptive carried out in the surgical department & orthopedics department in General Hospital, Lahore from August 2017 to March 2019. Sixty patients suffering from the spinal TB were the part of his research work who got admission through emergency department of the same hospital. Fifty five percent (n: 33) patients were males & 45.0% (n: 27) were female's patients. The range of the age of patients was from 14 to 36 years. The average age of the patients was thirty-three years. We noted the clinical aspects of all the patients & we collected the elaborated information of the patients on a well-organized Performa. Confirm patients of spinal TB were the part of this research work. Patients diagnosed with no tuberculosis were not the part of this research work.

Results: The very frequent symptom was backache in 63.0% (n: 38) patients. We found the compression of the spinal cord in 26.60% (n: 16) patients. Very frequent affected level was the thoracolumbar spine present in 45.0%. We found the diffuse contribution as very rare & only 5.0% (n: 3) patients were available with the involvement of more than one level. The most basic modality of imaging was the plain radiography. The most important effective investigation was MRI. The findings of the MRI for spinal TB were decreased intervertebral space between discs in 95.0% patients, wedge body collapse in 30.0% (n: 18) patients, whole body destruction in 20.0% (n: 12) & para-spinal abscess in 40.0% (n: 24) patients. We found the calcification in 30.0% (n: 18) patients & cord compression in 26.60% (n: 16) patients.

Conclusion: The most effective and valuable investigation in the patients suffering from spinal TB is MRI. It provides the data about the disease extend & it is the best method to provide guidelines for the surgical intervention. The use of the MRI is necessary during the follow up to check the response of the whole treatment.

Key Words: Destruction, methodology, compression, MRI, spinal, TB, suffering, response, treatment, therapy, discs.

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis is the complication of old times with a well-known history. It is still available with very high occurrence. This disease is accountable for high rate of morbidity & mortality in the highly populated areas of the countries which are under development [1]. Approximately 5% to 10% patients were available with infections of bone & joint [2]. There is positive sensitivity & culture in 80.0% patients [3]. There is very high danger of damage of cord because of pressure of abscess, displacement of the bone or ischemia from thrombosis of the spinal artery. This are the potts, paraplegia [4]. There can be the development of the paraplegia in 20.0% to 25.0% patients [2].

In accordance with the WHO, about 2 million persons in the world are available with TB [5]. Every year, six million people are acquiring the illness of TB. Two million people die because of this disease each year in the whole world [6]. The increase in the prevalence has association with the related rise in TB of joints & bones [7]. In the countries which are under development, tuberculosis of spine is a serious problem of health. The most fatal and frequent type of TB is musculoskeletal TB [8-10]. Plain radiography is basic modality of imaging utilized in each patient suffering from the spinal tuberculosis [11]. Most valuable method for the check and treatment of TB is MRI [12]. The examination of MRI in a sequence is best to check the treatment response [13, 14].

The features of MRI for the infection of TB are edema of soft tissues [12, para-spinal mass [15], narrowing of the space between discs, vertebral collapse & Kyphosis. This is very hard to distinguish among TB & pyogenic spondylitis. The availability of the calcification shows the TB [16].

METHODOLOGY

This research work carried out in the surgical unit and orthopedic department of General Hospital Lahore from August 2018 to March 2019. There were total sixty patients in this research work. The patients from both genders, with range of age from 14 to 46 years & only the identified patients of TB were the part of this research work. The patients with no TB were not the part of this research work. We used a wellorganized Performa in this research work. The identification of the disease was depending upon the past history, medical examination & investigations. Investigations contained the X-ray of the chest, ESR, sputum cytology & CBC. The research work was depending upon the MRI of the spine to assess the various radiological aspects of TB. We conducted the X-ray for all the patients as primary modality of imaging. No patient underwent computed tomography.

RESULTS

There were total sixty patients in this research work. Fifty five percent (n: 33) were male patients & 45.0% (n: 27) were the female patients. The range of the age of patients was 14 to 46 years. The average age of the patients was thirty three years. The scan of MRI displayed that maximum affected spine level was lower thoracic & upper lumber (45.0%) available in twenty seven patients. The involvement of thoracic spine was present in 23.30 (n: 14) patients. The involvement of the lumber spine was available in 20.0% (n: 12) patients. TB of cervical spine was present in 6.60% (n: 4) patients. We found a diffuse involvement in only 5.0% (n: 3) patients. MRI displayed the narrowing of the space between intervertebral discs in 95.0% patients. The very frequent symptom was the pain in the lower back. Local tenderness was the most frequent sign. The distribution of the disease according to the region in the spine TB is present in Table-1.

Table-I: Region wise distribution of TB spine cases

Spinal Site	No. of Occurrences	Percent
Cervical	4.0	6.600%
Thoracic	14.0	23.400%
Thoraco lumber	27.0	45.000%
Lumber	12.0	20.000%
Diffuse involvement	3.0	5.000%

The compression of the spinal cord was available in 26.60% (n: 16) patients. The scanning MRI displayed the narrowing of space between discs in 95.0% patients. The compression of cord was present in 26.60% patients.

DISCUSSION:

Spine TB was very frequent orthopedic & neurological abnormality until the mid of the previous century for the countries which were under development. This displayed a continuous decrease in the occurrence of this complication in the modern countries in 1960s & 1970s because of the effectualness of the programs of the public health & development in the field of chemotherapy [14]. Spine TB is still very common issue of health in the countries which are under development in comparison with the developed regions [17]. The causes for the disparities are low level of education, poorness, adverse conditions of hygiene, improper dietary habits, overpopulation, low budget involvement in the health programs and high occurrence of the pulmonary tuberculosis.

The dominance of the males & clinical pattern of the start of the disease described in this current research work is similar to the observations of the Jalleh R.D [14]. The vertebra's regional distribution is just same to the outcome of the research work of Bikha Ram [18] & Tulsi S.M [19]. There is very vital role of the plain radiography in the identification of the most of the patients suffering from spine tuberculosis [11]. For the early diagnosis of this disease, the most valuable investigation tool is MRI [12]. This was also very valuable investigation method for the evaluation & the treatment of the spine tuberculosis [8]. This method

provides the following data to the professionals about patients with spine tuberculosis.

1. Participation site
2. Swelling, abscess, of the para-vertebral soft tissues
3. Total quantity of the involved vertebra
4. Kyphosis angle
5. Vertebral canal's size
6. Degree of the compression of cord
7. The seriousness of the bone complication.

Though MRI is one of the expensive investigations but it provides with more information about the involvement of the soft tissues & degree of the compression of the cord or spinal root in comparison with the computed tomography and plain X-Ray [11, 15]. It provides us with the information regarding degree of the disease & provides the treatment grade. This is also very helpful for the checking of the treatment response with its application in a sequence [12]. Anti-TB drugs can react against the causative materials & can reach the spine cavity [20]. If there is extreme involvement of the bone together with compression of root or cord, the only treatment is the surgical intervention [21-23].

CONCLUSION:

The findings of his research work conclude that MRI of the spine is very effective and valuable examination of the assessment of the spinal TB. It provides us about the degree of the participation of the soft & bones and it also support us to formulate the method for the management of the treatment. It also support in the checking of the response of the treatment with regular scans of MRI in follow ups.

REFERENCES:

1. T Duck Worth, Chronic infection, Lecture notes on Orthopedics and Fractures, Blackwell scientific publication, Oxford 1984.
2. National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID). Microbes in sickness and in health. 2005. Retrieved on 3 October 2006. *J Pak Ortho Assoc* 2008;20(1):25.
3. Onyebujoh, Philip and Rook, Graham AW. World Health Organization Disease Watch: Focus: Tuberculosis. December 2004, Accessed 07 October 2006.
4. Watts HG, Lifese RM. Tuberculosis of Bones and Joints. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1996;78:288-98.
5. Farar S, Lowell AM, Meador MP. Extrapulmonary tuberculosis in the United States. *Am J Epidemiol* 1979;109:205.
6. Tulsi SM. Tuberculosis of the spine. In *Textbook of Tuberculosis*. New Dehli: Vikas publishing House Pvt Ltd. 1981;420-33.
7. Turgut M. Spinal tuberculosis (Pott's disease): its clinical presentation, surgical management, and outcome. A surgery study on 694 patients. *Neurosurg Rev* 2001;24(1):8-13.
8. Nasreen. Role of plain radiography in diagnosis of Koches spine *J Pak Ortho Assoc* 2008;20(1):25.
9. *Imaging in Orthopedics-Baily and love short practice of surgery* 25th edition. Arnold Press. UK. Year is Missing
10. Boxer DL, Pratt C, Hine AL, Radiological features during and following treatment of spinal tuberculosis. *Br J Radiol* 1992;65(774):476-9.
11. Jallah RD, Kuppusamy I, Mahayuddin AA. Spinal tuberculosis: a five years review of cases at the National Tuberculosis Centre. *Med J Malaya* 1991;46(3):269-73.
12. Greenspan A, Montesano P. "Pyogenic and Non Pyogenic Infections of the spine"; Time Condom, imaging if the spine in the practice, wolfe publishing, Mosby 1993;13.5-13.7.
13. Penter Renton, "Periosteal Reactions: Bone and Joint Infection; sarciod", David Sutton. *Textbook of Radiology and Imaging, Volume-II, 7th Edition*, Churchill Livingstone, 2003;1167.
14. Muckey T, Schutz T, Kirschner M. Psoas abscess: the spine as a primary source of infection. *Spine* 2003;28(6):E 106-13.
15. RamDevrjni B, Ghori RA, Momon N. Spinal Tuberculosis at Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad/ Jamshoro. *JLUMHS* 2006;(1-4):33-9.
16. Tulsi SM. Treatment of neurological complications in tuberculosis of the spine. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1969;51- A:680-92.
17. *TB infection Apley's system of Orthopedic and fracture*, 8th edition, Arnold, Oxford University Press Inc, New York 2001.
18. Raut AA, Narlawar RS, Nagar A. An unusual case of CV junction tuberculosis presenting with quadriplegia *Spine* 2003;28(15):E309.
19. Sinha S, Singh A, Gupta V. Surgical management and outcome of tuberculosis at lantoaxial dislocation: A 15 years experience. *Neurosurgery* 2003;52(2):331-8; discussion 338-9.
20. Vidyasager C, Murthy HK. Spinal tuberculosis with neurological deficit. *Natl Med J India* 1996;9(1):25-7.
21. Naveed M. Tuberculosis of spine: Pattern of the disease in Pakistan. *Professional Med J* 2001;28(6):E 106-13.
22. Bennet JC, Bennet SJ. *Infection of Bone and Joint*. Surgery international, 2006;73, Elsevier Ltd. ISSN 09554572.
23. *TB infection Apley's system of Orthopedic and fracture*, 8th edition, Arnold, Oxford University Press Inc, New York 2001.